

Sultanova H.J.
associate professor of the department of foreign languages

**THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE USE OF INTERNET
TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH**

Annotation: *The most urgent task of today is the improvement of foreign language teaching technologies through the use of Internet resources, their didactic description and active implementation in the educational process. This article explains theoretical foundations of the use of Internet technologies in the process of teaching English.*

Key words: *Internet, Information Communication Technology, Internet resources, theoretical foundations, teaching English.*

In today's world, knowledge of a foreign language, primarily English, is vital for anyone who wants to succeed in their profession, to be competent, to possess a whole range of intellectual, professional and communication skills.

The transition to the information society required effective informatization of education, based on the introduction of new information and communication technologies, which today are increasingly called Internet technologies.

The Internet (from Latin *inter* - between and English *net* - network, web) is "a worldwide computer network of electronic communications that unites regional, national and other networks" (Belyakov 2009: 54).

Today, more and more often the Internet is called the World Wide Web, the popularity of which is growing all over the world. To date, the number of users of the Web on Earth has reached the presence of three billion.

The English word "computer" means "programmable digital processor of various data".

With the advent of personal computers - household (home) and educational (school) ample opportunities arose to use them in teaching foreign languages.

The active introduction of computers in the learning process has been and is being carried out in several directions, provided for by the programs of different countries in the field of education:

CAI - Computer-Assisted Instruction

CAL - Computer-Assisted Learning

CAT - Computer-Assisted Teaching

CBE – Computer-Based Education

CML - Computer-Managed Learning.

All these areas are focused on "computer-assisted" teaching, learning, learning and management of the educational process.

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At the end of the 80s, a new independent direction of didactics and methods of teaching languages appeared - computer linguadidactics, which deals with theoretical issues of computerization of teaching a foreign language.

There is a huge number of terms related to the problem under consideration: database, information technology, computer technology, Internet technology, interactive mode, telecommunications, interface, distance learning, project methods, etc.

We analyzed a number of scientific studies in the field of computerization of teaching foreign languages. As a result, we were able to get an idea of how computer linguadidactics developed, what problems of using the Internet were discussed by scientists from different countries.

Early research articles of the 1980s were largely devoted to teaching students how to use a computer, the ability to work freely on a personal computer, and improving computer literacy (Maslyko 1997, Mashbits et al. 1988, Anderson 1988, etc.).

A large number of works in the 80s and 90s were devoted to the very phenomenon called "computerization in the educational process", "computer revolution", the importance and necessity of using all these processes in education were comprehended (Zvegintsev 1986, Kokkota 1986, Gershunsky 1987, Piotrovsky 1988, Mashbits 1989, Protasenya, Shtemenko 1995; Ahmad, Corbet 1985, Briefly, Kemble 1991, etc.).

In the late 80s, 90s and early 2000s, the psychological and pedagogical problems of using computers in the educational process, the psychological consequences of computerization, the mental states of PC users, taking into account their psychophysiological, age and personality characteristics were actively discussed (Tikhomirov 1986, Gorelov 1987, Mashbits 1988, Gur'eva 1993, Prokhorov 1995, Azimov 2000, etc.).

For the last 16 years, the minds of psychologists, linguists and methodologists have been occupied with the development, creation and active implementation of all kinds of Internet technologies in the educational process and, in particular, in the process of teaching foreign languages in schools, gymnasiums, and universities.

The teaching capabilities of these technologies, the problems of methodological expediency of their use, the motivation and effectiveness of learning a foreign language when working with a computer are studied.

I would especially like to emphasize the importance of the publications of scientists from the Tambov State University named after V.I. G.R. Derzhavina P.V. Sysoeva and M.N. Evstigneeva. They own recommendations on the introduction of new educational Internet materials in teaching English (2008), on the use of modern Internet resources in teaching a foreign language and culture (2008). They developed educational Internet resources in a foreign language (2009), Web 2.0 technologies in creating a virtual educational environment for learning foreign languages (2009). Finally, the handbook "Methods of teaching a

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foreign language using new information and communication technologies" (2010), as well as the textbook "Information and communication technologies in linguistic education" (2015) became a useful textbook for teachers, graduate students and students.

So, at present, the relevance and relevance of the Internet in the process of teaching foreign languages is beyond doubt. The main question today is how to apply existing Internet technologies, which of them are effective for teaching the language aspects of the language, which ones are for teaching activities (this will be discussed in the next chapter).

But first of all, it is necessary to consider the psychological and didactic aspects of the possibility of using Internet technologies in English lessons for students of the fifth to seventh grades, to determine the place and role of the Internet in the lesson: for what, at what stage of the lesson, to what extent it should be used.

List of used literature:

1. Anderson D. Teaching language with the help of a computer // Educational Issues. - 1988. - No. 4. - S. 70-85.
2. Belaya T.N., Bely Yu.A. Computerization of teaching English // Foreign languages at school. - 1998. - No. 1. - P.32-35.
3. Gorelov I.N. Conversation with a computer: Psycholinguistic aspect of problems. - M., 1987. - 256 p.
4. Komelev N.G. Dictionary of foreign words. – M.: EKSMO-Press, 2000. – 672 p.
5. Polat E.S. Internet at foreign language lessons // Inostr. languages at school. - 2001. - No. 2.3.

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